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The effect of carbon taxonomy on renewable hydrogen production: A techno-economic and environmental assessment

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ABSTRACT

From navigating the rainbow of colours to the lack of consensus in establishing a common taxonomy, the labelling and definition of green or renewable hydrogen presents a growing challenge. In this context, carbon taxonomy is understood through five critical aspects: carbon intensity, temporal and geographical correlation, additionality of renewable energy generation, and different system boundaries in Life Cycle Assessment (LCA). This study examines the effect of carbon taxonomy on the design and operation of Power-to-Gas (PtG) systems for renewable hydrogen production, including the electricity supply portfolio via Power Purchase Agreements (PPA) and grid-connected electrolysis. To this end, an optimisation model combining energy system modelling and LCA is developed and then applied to a case study in the Japanese context. The importance of the PPA portfolio in securing cheap and low-carbon electricity to produce hydrogen is addressed. To support this evaluation process, an eco-efficiency metric is introduced and proved to be a comprehensive tool for evaluating renewable hydrogen production. Regarding carbon taxonomies, the findings emphasize additionality as the key determinant factor, followed by temporal correlation and the definition of carbon intensity thresholds. The application of a cradle-to-gate LCA boundary influenced the carbon intensity accounting, playing an unexpected role on the design and optimal PtG dispatch strategy.

1. Introduction

At the 28th Conference of Parties (COP28) to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change, held in Dubai, United Arab Emirates, in November 2023, over 30 countries agreed to a Declaration of Intent (DoI). This Declaration focused on the mutual recognition of certification schemes for renewable and low-carbon hydrogen, along with its derivatives. This significant development underscores the imperative to establish an internationally accepted framework towards defining how green hydrogen must be produced in order to be considered renewable while following the principles of traceability, transparency, and sustainability [1].

Accordingly, two standardised methodologies were recognised to assess the GHG emissions associated with the production and transportation of hydrogen: the International Organisation for Standardisation ISO/TS 19870:2023 [2] and the Hydrogen Certification 101, developed in a joint effort by the International Partnership for Hydrogen

and Fuel Cells in the Economy (IPHE) and the Hydrogen Technology Collaboration Programme from the International Energy Agency (IEA H2 TCP) [3]. Both state that the Greenhouse Gas (GHG) intensity shall be calculated in Carbon Dioxide (CO₂) emissions generated throughout the entire production process to produce hydrogen with a minimum purity of 99.9% volume and a gauge pressure of at least 3 MPa. However, this definition leaves room for interpretation on how to account for the carbon intensity of hydrogen production. Particularly, around the five main elements covered by the latest Delegated Act (RED II) on hydrogen from the European Commission [4], and subsequently in the US Inflation Reduction Act [5]: (i) the carbon intensity of the hydrogen to be qualified as renewable, clean or green hydrogen, (ii) the additionality and geographic criteria ensuring that renewable hydrogen production grows in hand with new, additional and local, Renewable Energy Sources (RES) within the same electricity market zone, (iii) the temporal correlation between RES generation and hydrogen production to account for the carbon intensity. (iv) Geographical correlation which

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restricts the electric supply depending on bidding zones and price differentials, (v) the applying Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) boundaries to the calculation of the carbon intensity.

Table 1 offers a non-exhaustive comparative overview of different publicly available carbon taxonomy schemes and how the previously mentioned criteria differ. Notably, the geographical correlation criteria have been left out of the scope of the present paper.

The selected case study will focus on the Japanese context, which besides being one of the countries subscribing to the DoI, Japan was the first to publish a national hydrogen roadmap in 2017 [6]. Following the success in leading the development of Liquefied Natural Gas (LNG) in the 20th century [7], Japan has taken the forefront in initiating and showcasing global supply chains for importing hydrogen and its derivatives: liquefied hydrogen, ammonia and liquid organic hydrogen carriers [8–11].

The latest published Green Transformation Act (GX) draft from February 2023 aimed to accelerate decarbonisation in Japan to achieve its goal of cutting 46% of carbon emissions by 2030, relative to 2013 levels, and becoming carbon neutral by 2050. In this strategy towards decarbonisation, hydrogen plays a central role as a means to reduce the high dependency on fossil fuel imports – around 83.5% in 2022 [12], while enhancing national energy self-sufficiency through a versatile and renewable energy carrier across various sectors [13]. Moreover, in June 2023, Japan's Hydrogen Basic Strategy was updated to keep up with the latest international moves in the sector: the EU's Green Deal Industrial Plan [14] and the US Inflation Reduction Act [5]. In this updated report, Japan established a carbon taxonomy for renewable and low-carbon hydrogen differentiation: 3.4 kg of CO₂ emissions or less per 1 kg of hydrogen produced, including transportation and conversion in the carbon footprint accounting for imported hydrogen [15]. However, how this carbon footprint is going to be accounted for in terms of geographical and temporal correlation remains unaddressed in a national strategy that heavily relies on and even prioritises grey and blue hydrogen imports [16]. This ambiguity between renewable and fossil-based hydrogen, supported by a potentially uninformed population split on the choice between green hydrogen and grey hydrogen production [17], can eventually lead to negligible, uncertain or even negative effects on emission reductions, as in the case of co-firing fossil-sourced hydrogen and ammonia – where the Japanese JERA is planning to co-fire ammonia and coal at a rate of about 50% by 2030 [18]. These issues are particularly pressing for a country that aims to incorporate 12 million tonnes of hydrogen through a combination of imports and domestic production by 2040 [15].

Furthermore, as addressed through the concept of additionality, deploying additional renewable electricity capacity is key to ensuring renewable low-carbon hydrogen production that does not exhaust the existing RES. In this aspect, corporate Power Purchase Agreements (PPA) are an essential tool to guarantee stable, long-term agreements essential for enhancing the economic viability of hydrogen projects and ensuring a consistent rise in domestic production capabilities. However, while corporate PPAs are on the rise in Japan, the scale of power

generation they cover remains modest due to the currently low proportion of renewables within Japan's overall energy mix and the slow adoption of corporate PPAs, representing less than 1% of the globally contracted volume [19].

In the present paper, we aim to showcase a model that, in the first instance, allows for optimally designing a grid-connected, or not, renewable hydrogen PtG system. This hybrid renewable energy system combines two virtual PPA options: Wind Power (WP) and solar Photovoltaic power (PV). Then, it integrates a Battery Energy Storage System (BESS) along with a hydrogen gas buffer to supply a target stable demand of hydrogen per day, month and/or year. On a broader scope, the paper is also relevant for policy-making, contributing to the techno-economic and environmental evaluation of the effects of the different carbon taxonomies and certification schemes in renewable hydrogen production. The developed model is then applied to the Japanese context through the case study of the Awaji Island.

2. Literature review

These recent policy developments regarding the carbon footprint accountability of renewable and low-carbon hydrogen have reached the scientific literature, confirming the lack of an agreement on the labelling and carbon accounting while spotting the unsuitability of the existing schemes for fair global trade [17]. Inconsistent scope definitions and terminology misinterpretation could lead to a global mismatch in certification, difficulting the achievement of the targets for global hydrogen trade [20], further compromised by the proliferation of divergent legislation [21], certification schemes, terminology and gaps in the standards [22].

Regarding the definition of the LCA and the system boundaries, Table 1 showed a partial agreement on undertaking a well-to-gate approach, meaning that the embodied emissions are beyond the boundary; thus, only accounting for the carbon footprint of the electricity consumed [23]. However, previous literature has already pointed out the risks of leaving the manufacturing impact out of the emissions threshold calculations [24], advocating for a cradle-to-gate approach, a choice predominantly preferred in the scientific literature [25]. In fact, from a social LCA perspective, the consideration of the manufacturing impact has been relevant to determine more socially just hydrogen production [26]. Furthermore, the interpretation of “production process emissions” as defined in the reference methodologies, has led to interchangeably misapplication of the terms cradle-to-gate and well-to-gate, even within the same certification scheme [27–29]. This LCA dimension has been missing in previous studies addressing the different elements of the carbon taxonomy such as temporal correlation [30], or the optimal design of Power-to-Gas (PtG) [31]. Even the carbon intensity of renewable energy sources (RES), which often overlooked when calculating the carbon emissions of electrolytic hydrogen [32], posed a risk of underestimating total emissions [24]. Through the present Paper, we aim to provide with new insights in this topic by analysing and comparing the implications of both well-to-gate and cradle-to-gate

Table 1
Overview of different international carbon taxonomy schemes.

Carbon taxonomy scheme	Organisation, Country	Carbon intensity (kgCO ₂ -eq/kgH ₂)	System boundaries	Additionality	Temporal correlation
Green hydrogen standard	Green hydrogen Association	1	Well-to-gate	Not defined	Yearly
Low carbon hydrogen standard	United Kingdom	2	Well-to-gate	Required	30-min matching with monthly average
Low-carbon hydrogen certification system	Japan	3.4	Well-to-gate	Not defined	Not defined
Renewable energy directive II	European Union	3.4	Well-to-wheel	Required	Monthly until 2027, then hourly
Clean-hydrogen production tax credit	United States	4	Well-to-gate	Required	Yearly until 2028, then monthly
CertifHy	European Union	4.4	Well-to-gate	Not defined	Not defined
Standard and evaluation of low carbon hydrogen	China	4.9	Well-to-gate	Not defined	Not defined

system boundaries.

Extensive literature investigates the environmental impacts of renewable hydrogen production using LCA and sustainability assessment. Various studies have analysed the environmental implications of the main electrolyser cell technologies: Alkaline (AECs), Proton Exchange Membrane (PEMECs) and Solid Oxide (SOECs) [33–35]. Although PEMECs were consistently identified as the technology with the highest GHG impact, mostly due to the inclusion of Platinum Group Materials (PGM) in the stack manufacturing – platinum on the cathode side and iridium on the anode. Furthermore, several studies have addressed the GHG impact of electricity consumption during the use stage, and the impact of different temporal correlations, confirming hourly time-matching requirements as an effective way to limit emissions on hydrogen emissions reduction at a systemic level [30,36,37]. All these studies agreed on the negligible impact of the manufacturing stage when compared to the electricity consumption during hydrogen production for the whole lifetime of the electrolyser and, therefore, neglected the manufacturing impact when accounting for carbon intensity. Unaddressed in these existing studies remains, whether the manufacturing impact is negligible when accounting for the GHG impact at the hourly level.

Then, regarding the economic impacts, while a more systemic approach found the economic impact of hourly correlation negligible with an impact below 1USD per kg of hydrogen [36], contemporary studies in Europe evaluated, that the definition of renewable hydrogen highly impacts the feasibility and design of the power-to-gas system, suggesting that hourly time matching results in oversizing of electrolyser plants [38–40]. Furthermore, hourly temporal matching increases the entry barriers, requiring higher RES portfolio diversification for certain cases, or geographies [41]. In the end, maximising the full-load hours of operation is a pivotal point in reducing the overall cost of hydrogen production [42], and hourly time correlation leads to more complex dispatch strategies for optimal operation of the electrolysers [43]. Notably, the unrestricted consumption of grid's electricity was found not to necessarily increase carbon intensity, which profoundly impacted the techno-economic viability of renewable hydrogen production [32].

Among these studies, the concept of additionality, which has been spotted as the most differential aspect to comply with when designing and evaluating the feasibility of a PtG project [44], faced diverse modelling interpretations. On the one hand, additionality was defined as a positive net balance of energy exports and imports between the contracted additional RES and the grid for the given time correlation [39]. Similarly, additionality was also modelled by matching generation and electrolysis consumption, allowing grid-connection support [30]. At systemic level, additionality has been addressed from a “compete” versus “non-compete” lens, depending on whether the contracted RES optimisation happens in parallel or in series with the grid resource optimisation for different baseline and/or future grid scenarios [37]. This scenario-based study, while valid for the systemic level [30], might be too vague when assessing a local project or designing a site for a specific hydrogen demand – remaining unaddressed [39,40], or not included in the size optimisation problem [38,41]. Even despite the explicit mention of PPAs in the regulation [4], none of the previous studies have addressed or modelled the sizing and financial effects of PPAs.

Furthermore, despite the intrinsic combination of technical, economic, and environmental factors when linking aspects like the Levelised Cost of Hydrogen (LCOH), the investment cost, the carbon intensity, or the CO₂ emissions, no attempt is made to pursue new metrics interconnecting the environmental and economic performance of the hydrogen produced. In this regard, other studies have employed Eco-Efficiency (EE) metrics to analyse the effect of CO₂ emission restrictions on different hydrogen production pathways as a global indicator [45], to valorise fuel production methods, as in the case of hydrogen for bus mobility [46], or to benchmark a specific pathway, as in the case of biomass gasification [47]. However, no literature exists

that has implemented an EE indicator with a more dynamic approach for evaluating renewable hydrogen production at an hourly level.

Finally, concerning the production of renewable hydrogen in Japan, research at the systemic level confirmed that hydrogen can play a role in improving the efficiency of the whole energy system while reducing curtailment and total energy costs [48–51]. Renewable hydrogen production has also proved to have the potential to replace Steam Methane Reformers (SMR) by 2040 if the correct support is provided [52]. Furthermore, at the system level, the techno-economic viability of PEM electrolysis to produce renewable hydrogen within the envisioned national targets - 30 JPY/Nm³, or 333.92 JPY/kgH₂ [15], was addressed and conceived as possible if, again, the correct support is provided and market conditions for electrolysers and electricity pricing are met [53]. Additionally, via PEM electrolysis, renewable hydrogen production from an electric grid with high solar and wind power was also addressed as a means to provide flexibility services and coupling gas and the electric grid [54]. Other pathways, such as direct seawater electrolysis in remote locations, have been addressed techno-economically [55]. Some LCA studies on the hydrogen supply chains to reveal their environmental impacts exist [56,57]. However, the implications of a carbon taxonomy or any kind of carbon footprint accountability for domestic renewable hydrogen production remain unaddressed in the Japanese context.

Based on the previously reviewed literature, and the spotted gaps, we conclude that the scientific novelty of the present Article is divided into 3 different levels:

- Methodology — model: The presented optimisation model allows the optimal sizing of a power-to-gas system under different carbon taxonomies and temporal correlations. The novelty is found in the approach that combines techno-economic optimisation with LCA. The LCA is divided into two functional units, considering both the manufacturing and use-stage impacts and allowing for definition of different system boundaries.
- Methodology — metrics: For the first time, we developed a hydrogen EE metric to link hydrogen prices with carbon intensity and downstream GHG-saving potential.
- Case study—Japan: The model is applied to a real case study in Awaji Island, Hyogo Prefecture, Japan. The case study is based on real RES development and generation potential. Local renewable hydrogen production is analysed under different carbon taxonomy schemes, evaluating the effects of different system boundaries (cradle-to-gate and well-to-gate), temporal correlation and additionality in the Japanese context. The case study serves as a pivotal point to analyse the implications of the different carbon taxonomies.

3. Materials and methods

This study presents a novel optimisation model for the design of a power-to-gas system to supply a stable renewable hydrogen demand by considering the techno-economic and environmental dimensions. The layout of the proposed model is shown in Fig. 1:

Firstly, the GHG impact of renewable hydrogen production is obtained via an LCA. The system boundaries are set to include both manufacturing and use stage impacts, which are later on fed into the energy system model. Secondly, a Mixed Integer Linear Programming (MILP) algorithm programmed in Python, formulated in Pyomo and solved with Gurobi, optimises a combined sizing and power dispatch problem. The differentiation of the two loops, often jointly referred to as the optimal design algorithm, is the integration of the LCA input. According to the chosen system boundaries, different stages are to be considered. The manufacturing impact is scaled based on the optimal sizing loop, while the use stage is calculated based on the optimal power dispatch strategy achieved in the energy system, all under the given constraints, as e.g. the temporal correlation and carbon intensity value provided by a certain taxonomy. Hereafter, the carbon intensity of the renewable hydrogen production and the LCOH are calculated and

Fig. 1. Techno-economic and environmental optimisation model layout.

further combined to determine the EE metric for the reference energy system.

3.1. Multi-energy system model

The Multi-Energy System (MES) is modelled through an external power balance which involved the interaction at energy market level – PPA and electric grid, and an internal one, that considers the asset dispatch strategy, the BESS and electrolyser (see Fig. 2). The model is fed with historical data sets at hourly granularity comprising electric grid prices, carbon intensity, and power generation from the PV and WP PPAs.

3.1.1. Objective function breakdown

The objective of the model is to find the optimal power-to-gas design to supply a daily stable demand for hydrogen, formulated as a techno-economic optimisation subjected to environmental constraints. Hence, the objective function is defined by the minimisation of the total annualised cost, denoted as in Equation (1), which represents the minimisation of the sum of the annualised investment cost (C_{inv}), and the annual operation cost (C_{op}).

$$\min(C_{inv} + C_{op}) \quad (1)$$

The calculation of both terms in Equation (1), is further developed for each asset n , belonging to the total number of assets N in Equations (2)–(5). The C_{inv} , in Equation (2), is calculated as the product of the System Replacement Ratio (SRR_n), the Capital Expenditures ($CAPEX_n$), the capacity/size of the asset (Q_n) and the Capital Recovery Factor (CRF_n).

$$C_{inv} = \sum_n^N SRR_n \cdot CAPEX_n \cdot Q_n \cdot CRF_n \quad (2)$$

In Equation (3), the SRR_n represents the ratio between the lifetime of the asset ($Lifetime_n$) and the lifetime of the project ($Lifetime_{project}$). In Equation (4), CRF_n represents the annualisation of the asset cost considering the time value of money for discount rate d .

$$SRR_n = \frac{Lifetime_{project}}{Lifetime_n} \quad (3)$$

$$CRF_n = \frac{d \cdot (1 + d)^{Lifetime_n}}{(1 + d)^{Lifetime_n} - 1} \quad (4)$$

The C_{op} is then calculated in two terms; the first one is the product of the Operational Expenditures ($OPEX_n$) – expressed as a function of the capacity/size of the asset (Q_n). The second term represents the Cash Flows (CF), as the sum of the difference between cost and revenues. It is the financial aftermath of electricity imports ($P_{t,a}^{ext,im}$) and exports ($P_{t,a}^{ext,ex}$) in the external power balance, and the import ($\lambda_{t,a}^{im}$) and export tariffs ($\lambda_{t,a}^{ex}$). This aspect is further developed in the modelling of the PPAs in Chapter 3.1.4.

$$C_{op} = \sum_n^N OPEX_n \cdot Q_n + \sum_{t,a}^{T,A} (P_{t,a}^{im} \cdot \lambda_{t,a}^{im} - P_{t,a}^{ex} \cdot \lambda_{t,a}^{ex}) \quad (5)$$

3.1.2. Power balance and system operation

The external power balance in Equation (5) is complimentary to the internal power balance which involves the power dispatch over time of the assets: electrolyser ($P_{t,ely}$), and battery – charge, discharge ($P_{t,bess}^{ch}$, $P_{t,bess}^{dis}$).

$$P_{t,ely} + P_{t,bess}^{ch} - P_{t,bess}^{dis} - \sum_{t,a}^{T,A} P_{t,a}^{im} = 0 \quad (6)$$

Fig. 2. Layout of the energy system model. Legend: PPA (Power Purchase Agreement), PV (Photovoltaic Power), WP (Wind Power).

In Equation (7), the electrolyser's hydrogen output ($H2_{t,ely}$) is calculated based on efficiency η_{ely} – expressed in kgH_2/kWh , and a binary variable ($\beta_{t,ely}$) defining if the electrolyser is on/off. Equation (8) defines the electrolyser's operating range, bounded by the minimal partial load (P_{ely}^{mpl}) and the electrolyser capacity (Q_{ely}).

$$H2_{t,ely} = \beta_{t,ely} \cdot \eta_{ely} \cdot P_{t,ely} \quad (7)$$

$$P_{ely}^{mpl} \cdot Q_{ely} \leq P_{t,ely} \leq Q_{ely} \quad (8)$$

Regarding the characterisation of the BESS, its operational power range is defined by the product of the battery capacity (Q_{bess}) and the charge and discharge C-rates (C_{bess}^{dis} , C_{bess}^{ch}), Equations (9) and (10), respectively. Then, Equation (11) limits the operation of the BESS to only charge, or discharge, but not both simultaneously. Equation (12), forbids the BESS to charge from the grid. Equation (13) defines the State Of Charge over time ($SOC_{t,bess}$), while Equation (14) bounds its minimum (SOC_{bess}^{min}), and maximum as a function of the sizing Q_{bess} .

$$P_{t,bess}^{dis} \leq C_{bess}^{dis} \cdot Q_{bess} \quad (9)$$

$$P_{t,bess}^{ch} \leq C_{bess}^{ch} \cdot Q_{bess} \quad (10)$$

$$P_{t,bess}^{ch} \cdot P_{t,bess}^{dis} = 0 \quad (11)$$

$$P_{t,bess}^{ch} \cdot P_{t,grid}^{im} = 0 \quad (12)$$

$$SOC_{t,bess} = SOC_{t-1,bess} + P_{t,bess}^{ch} \cdot \eta_{bess} - P_{t,bess}^{dis} / \eta_{bess} \quad (13)$$

$$SOC_{bess}^{min} \cdot Q_{bess} \leq SOC_{t,bess} \leq Q_{bess} \quad (14)$$

Finally, Equation (15) defines SOC over time of the hydrogen storage buffer ($SOC_{t,hs}$), bounded by the minimal load (SOC_{hs}^{min}) and the tank capacity (Q_{hs}), in Equation (16). The objective hydrogen demand is introduced as an export ($H2_{t,demand}^{ex}$).

$$SOC_{t,hs} = SOC_{t-1,hs} + H2_{t,ely} - H2_{t,demand}^{ex} \quad (15)$$

$$SOC_{hs}^{min} \cdot Q_{hs} \leq SOC_{t,hs} \leq Q_{hs} \quad (16)$$

3.1.3. Temporal correlation and carbon intensity accountability

The accountability of the GHG impact is achieved in Equation (17) by calculating the carbon emissions ($CO2_t$) for a time step t . As described in the scope of the LCA, it takes into consideration the sum of two terms, the manufacturing impact of the electrolyser ($MI_{t,ely}$) and the use stage impact of the electricity consumption of the electrolyser ($USI_{t,ely}$). Then, in Equation (18), the carbon emissions are bounded by the applying carbon taxonomy ($CO2IL_{TC}$), which sets the maximum carbon intensity level $CO2IL$ of the net hydrogen production ($H2_{t,ely}$) for the time step defined in the temporal correlation TC , hourly, monthly or yearly.

$$CO2_t = MI_{t,ely} + USI_{t,ely} \quad (17)$$

$$CO2_{TC} \leq CO2IL_{TC} \cdot \sum_t^{TC} H2_{t,ely} \quad (18)$$

The manufacturing impact is calculated in Equation (19), based on the sizing and lifetime ($Lifetime_{t,ely}$) of the electrolyser expressed in hours, and the input provided by the LCA ($CO2(Q_{ely})$) – expressed in $kgCO_2 - eq/MW$, when the electrolyser is in operation ($\beta_{t,ely}$).

$$MI_{t,ely} = \beta_{t,ely} \cdot \frac{Q_{ely} \cdot CO2(Q_{ely})}{Lifetime_{t,ely}} \quad (19)$$

The use stage impact is then further developed in Equation (20),

where the different import power flows and their respective carbon intensities ($\theta_{t,a}$) are taken into account. Additionally, the manufacturing impact of the battery (θ_{bess}) – expressed in $kg - eq CO_2/kWh$, along with the carbon intensity of the power charged, which depends on the agent a , and discharged ($\theta_{t,soc}$), which represents the carbon intensity of the energy stored.

$$USI_{t,ely} = \sum_{t,a}^{T,A} (P_{t,a}^{im} \cdot \theta_{t,a} - P_{t,bess}^{ch} \cdot (\theta_{t,a} + \theta_{bess})) + P_{t,bess}^{dis} \cdot (\theta_{t,soc} + \theta_{bess}) \quad (20)$$

3.1.4. Additionality and Power Purchase Agreement

The application of additionality implies that hydrogen production contributes to reducing overall GHG emissions by providing new, additional sources of clean energy. For that purpose, additionality has been modelled, in Equation (21), through a binary variable add that enables or does not allow grid-supported electricity to supply the PtG system, enforcing the supply only via PPA.

$$P_{t,grid}^{im} \leq (1 - add) \cdot Q_{grid-access} \quad (21)$$

Furthermore, as described in the European taxonomy, the applicability of additionality can be relaxed based on two conditions that allow for grid-connected electrolysis without restriction: RES penetration above 90% or carbon intensity below $64.8 g - eq CO_2/kWh$.

The PPAs are assumed to be virtual off-site pay-as-produced PPAs; thus, the consumer takes in all the PPA's gross generation and is responsible for feeding in the surplus. This is achieved by applying an exclusive condition between grid imports and PPA exports in Equation (22). Furthermore, the PPA is sized, for PV (Q_{pvppa}) in Equation (23) and for WP (Q_{wppa}) and in Equation (24), according to the available irradiation (i_t) and wind speed (v_t) profiles.

$$(P_{t,pvppa}^{ex} + P_{t,wppa}^{ex}) \cdot P_{t,grid}^{im} = 0 \quad (22)$$

$$P_{t,pvppa}^{ex} + P_{t,pvppa}^{im} = Q_{pvppa} \cdot i_t \quad (23)$$

$$P_{t,wppa}^{ex} + P_{t,wppa}^{im} = Q_{wppa} \cdot v_t \quad (24)$$

3.2. Evaluation metrics

Besides the output from the optimisation in terms of capacity and dispatch variables, three metrics are further elaborated to analyse the results: (i) LCOH, (ii) Carbon Intensity Of Hydrogen (CIOH), and the connection between both of them, (iii) EE.

3.2.1. Levelised Cost of hydrogen (LCOH)

The LCOH is calculated in Equation (25) as the discounted sum of initial capital expenditures ($CAPEX_0$) and the annual operational expenses ($OPEX_y$), capital expenditures ($CAPEX_y$), and cash flows (CF_y) for the year y at a discount rate d over the project lifetime L . This total is then subtracted by the salvage value (S_L) at the end of the lifespan, and divided by the discounted sum of hydrogen production costs ($H2_y$) over the same lifespan.

$$LCOH = \frac{CAPEX_0 + \sum_{y=0}^L \frac{OPEX_y + CAPEX_y + CF_y}{(1+d)^y} - \frac{S_L}{(1+d)^L}}{\sum_{y=0}^L \frac{H2_y}{(1+d)^y}} \quad (25)$$

3.2.2. Carbon intensity of hydrogen (CIOH)

The CIOH calculation is presented following the expressions of the manufacturing ($MI_{t,ely}$) and use stage impacts ($USI_{t,ely}$) developed in

Chapter 3.1.3. In Equation (26), the CIOH is calculated for a given temporal correlation (TC) - hourly, monthly or yearly.

$$CIOH_{TC} = \frac{\sum_{t,a}^{TC,A} (MI_{t,ely} + USI_{t,ely})}{\sum_t^{TC} H2_{t,ely}} \quad (26)$$

3.2.3. Eco-efficiency (EE)

The EE metric is defined as the environmental efficiency at the given TC. It is presented in Equation (27), as the expression of the inverse of the CIOH plus the inverse of the LCOH. This equation includes the exchange parameter γ as a means to scaled up or down the LCOH based on the currency chosen. This represents an evaluation metric combining carbon intensity and economic factors associated with hydrogen energy. The higher the EE, the more economically competitive and environmental friendly the hydrogen. Thus, a high EE is desirable.

$$EE_{TC} = \frac{1}{CIOH_{TC}} + \gamma \cdot \frac{1}{LCOH} \quad (27)$$

3.3. Life Cycle Assessment

The LCA is a standardised method to compute the environmental impacts of products and services [58]. Both Cradle-to-Gate (CtG) and Well-to-Gate (WtG) approaches are considered for the present paper. In a CtG assessment, the system boundaries include the manufacturing stage, comprising raw material extraction and asset assembly of the electrolyser and the use stage, considering the impacts of the different power sources involved in the electricity supply of the electrolyser. Then, the WtG boundary only considers the use stage. As a functional unit, the production of 1 kg of hydrogen is chosen. However, the manufacturing impact was provided to the energy model in kilograms equivalent to CO₂ per MegaWatt (MW) of electrolyser capacity, while the use stage impact was provided in kilograms equivalent to CO₂ per kiloWatt-hour (kWh) of electricity.

The Climate Change (CC) of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) 2021 is used as a life cycle impact assessment methodology [59]. When available, data are extracted from the ecoinvent database version 3.9.1, allocation, cut-off and used to compile the life cycle inventories [60].

3.3.1. Manufacturing stage

For the calculation of the manufacturing impact, a Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) of a 1 MW PEM electrolysis plant assembled in Japan was developed. The core of the LCI of the electrolysis plant was based on an available Bill Of Materials (BOM) [61], which includes the Balance of Plant (BoP) and PEM stack. Then, the LCI has been further developed by considering the different sub-elements integrating the BoP and stack, according to research developed in the HyTech European project [62]. In addition, the Membrane Electrode Assembly (MEA), was further elaborated based on a PEM Fuel-Cell (FC), assuming the same weight distribution and manufacturing processes [63], and scaled up according to Ref. [61]. The LCI differentiated the following components: PEM, Gas Diffusion Layer (GDL), and catalyst layer. Further assumptions and proxies applied to the PEM and the catalyst layer:

- PEM: One of its essential elements is Nafion Perfluorinated-Sulfonic Acid (PFSA), synthesized from Perfluoroalkyl Sulfonyl Fluoride (PSF) and tetrafluoroethylene, with a ratio of 57.4 wt% TFE to 42.6 wt% PSF [64]. In the absence of PSF data in the ecoinvent database, sulfuric acid was employed as a substitute for the fluoride component [65].

- Catalyst layer: The catalyst layer includes both the cathode and anode inks. The composition for both anode and cathode inks has been described [66]. The ionomer Nafion 521's composition is extracted from a PEM FC's LCI [63]. The cathode is assumed to be made of platinum on carbon support (Pt/C), and the anode is assumed to be Iridium on carbon support (Ir/C) [61]. However, since Iridium is not available in the database, Rhodium is used as a proxy for Iridium due to its similar physical and chemical properties, and comparable mineral extraction process since they share the same ore [67].

3.3.2. Use stage

The use stage impact, as described in the formulation, accounts for the carbon intensity of the electricity supplied to the electrolyser. Therefore, three main sources are to be considered: (i) the electric grid, PPA, and BESS, defined by their manufacturing impact and the carbon intensity of the electricity supplied.

The electric grid's hourly carbon intensity is based on the energy mix of the energy market where the electrolysis plant is located, yearly data for the relevant countries is obtained from available online at Electricity Maps [68]. Then, the carbon intensity of the electricity supplied by the two potential virtual PPA options considered, photovoltaic installations and wind turbines, is based on the literature: a CC impact of 12 gCO₂-eq/kWh for the wind PPA [69,70], and 50 gCO₂-eq/kWh for the PV PPA [71,72].

In a similar fashion, for the BESS, the GHG impact of a lithium-ion battery for stationary applications is obtained from literature and is 75 kgCO₂-eq/kWh of capacity [73]. As the battery only serves to supply the hydrogen production, the manufacturing impacts are allocated fully to the use stage. Manufacturing impacts are calculated by multiplying the climate change impact of the lithium-ion battery with the lifetime capacity based on the cycles, by the sizing model of the energy model. Second, the carbon intensity of the energy dispatched through the battery is determined by the source of the electricity, either PV or wind PPA, and only counted as part of the use stage impact on the hydrogen production when the battery is discharged.

3.4. Case study: The Awaji Island

The chosen case study for this assessment focuses on Awaji Island, located in Hyogo Prefecture, Japan. Situated in the western part of Osaka Bay, Awaji Island boasts abundant renewable energy sources (RES). Its strategic location positions it as a potential hub for exporting energy to neighbouring regions in the Kansai area, which currently heavily relies on energy imports [17], also shown by its negative energy export balance in Fig. 3.

The Awaji Island has been recognised as a Special Comprehensive Zone in the framework of the National Energy Strategy and aims to become a sustainable region through the Awaji Green Future Project [75]. Moreover, the island is included in the ambitions of the New Energy and Industrial Technology Development Organisation (NEDO), within the framework of the Development of Technologies for Realising a Hydrogen Society report, a comprehensive examination was conducted on the potential of a hybrid power-to-gas system in conjunction with batteries to alleviate grid congestion on the island [76].

3.4.1. Parametrisation and assumptions

The historical techno-economic and environmental data used in the parametrisation of the model was recollected for a year-long period between April 1, 2022 and March 30, 2023. The power generation profile for the existing RES in Awaji Island was obtained from Kansai Transmission and Distribution [77]. Then, the potential RES availability

Fig. 3. Renewable energy export potential of Kansai region, Japan. Source: Energy Sustainability Laboratory of Tohoku University, Japan Energy Database (Version 2.9), <https://energy-sustainability.jp> [74].

Table 2

Agent's techno-economic data overview. Legend: photovoltaic panels (PV), wind power (WP), power purchase agreement (PPA), not applicable (NA).

Agent [Referece]	Sizing limit (MW)	Tariff (JPY/kWh)	Feed-in-Tariff (JPY/kWh)	Surcharge (JPY/kWh)	Carbon intensity (kgCO ₂ -eq/kWh)
Electric grid [68,78]	NA	19.6 ^a	NA	3.5	400 ^a
PV PPA [71,72,79]	10	10	10	3.5	50
WP PPA [69,70,79]	10	36	36	3.5	12

^a Average value, a data series at hourly granularity has been considered.

and export capacity were scaled based on measurements and publicly available data from Tohoku University [74]. The electricity prices for the Kansai energy market were obtained from the Japan Electric Power Exchange [78]. The carbon intensity of the grid electricity mix was obtained from Electricity Maps [68].

The techno-economic assumptions for the PPAs are based on the regulation and pricing defined by the Japanese Ministry of Energy, Transport and Industry (METI) [79]. Accordingly, a consumption surcharge for all energy consumption and a fixed feed-in tariff (FiT) for all RES injected into the grid are assumed. In this study, the PPA prices of WP and PV are set equal to the FiT specified for each resource – 36 and 10 JPY respectively, as shown in Table 2. Consequently, any excess power injected beyond the contracted PPA incurs a financial loss due to the surcharge price [80].

Then, following the mathematical formulation of the MES model

Table 3

Asset's techno-economic data overview. Legend: Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESS), Capital Expenditures (CAPEX), Operational Expenditures (OPEX), Minimum Partial Load (MPL), efficiency (η), C-rate (C), State Of Charge (SOC), Hydrogen (H₂), Carbon Dioxide (CO₂), not applicable (NA).

Asset [Referece]	Sizing limit	CAPEX	OPEX (as a %of CAPEX)	Lifetime	Technical parameters	Manufacturing impact
Electrolyser [81]	10 MW	330 kJPY/kW 2000 EUR/kW	5 %	10 years 80,000 h	MPL = 5% $\eta = 54 \text{ kWh/kgH}_2$	150 kgCO ₂ -eq/kW
BESS [73]	10 MWh	80 kJPY/kWh 500 EUR/kWh	3 %	10 years 4000 cycles	$\eta = 0.9 \text{ C} = 0.5 \text{ SOC}_{\min} = 0.2 \text{ SOC}_{t=0} = 0.5$	75 kgCO ₂ -eq/kW
Hydrogen storage [82]	50 tons H ₂	50 kJPY/kg 300 EUR/kg	0.5 %	20	$\text{SOC}_{\min} = 0.2 \text{ SOC}_{t=0} = 0.5$	NA

Table 4

Overview of the 24 scenarios based on international carbon taxonomies. Legend: Yearly (Y), Monthly (M), Hourly (H), United States of America (USA), United Kingdom (UK), Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), Well-to-Gate (WtG), Cradle-to-Gate (CtG).

Scenario	Carbon Intensity	Temporal Correlation	Additionality	System boundaries
Baseline	3.4	Y	Unapplied	WtG
Japan	3.4	Y, M and H	Applied and unapplied	CtG and WtG
China	4.9	Y, M and H	Applied and unapplied	CtG and WtG
USA	4	Y, M and H	Applied and unapplied	CtG and WtG
UK	2	Y, M and H	Applied and unapplied	CtG and WtG

Fig. 4. The effect of different carbon taxonomy on the LCOH. Legend: UK (United Kingdom), US (United States), CtG (Cradle-to-Gate), WtG (Well-to-Gate), H (hourly), M (monthly), Y (yearly).

have been simulated for the Japanese context, involving the three temporal correlations and application, or not, of the additionality principle. Then, the carbon taxonomy adopted by China, the United Kingdom (UK) and the United States of America (USA) have also been included, adding up to a total of 24 scenarios (see Table 4).

4. Results and discussion

This section presents the results and analysis of applying the optimisation model to the scenarios outlined in Chapter 3.4.3 of the case study. The findings are divided in two parts. First, the three KPIs LCOH, COIH and EE are addressed. Then, the analysis focuses on the design and operation implication taking the Japanese taxonomy as a reference.

- KPI analysis: LCOH, COIH and EE.

Fig. 4 shows the lowest LCOH results achieved for each of the 48 proposed scenarios. The lowest LCOH achieved under the given assumptions showed, that the cost reality of renewable hydrogen production is still very far away from the 333.92 JPY/kgH₂ envisioned target of Japan’s Basic Hydrogen Strategy. An LCOH of 2153 JPY/kgH₂ was obtained, which is nearly seven times higher than the 2030 national target.

Despite the carbon intensity threshold being a distinctive element in the definition of the taxonomies, the results proved that additionality was the most determinant factor in the LCOH, followed by temporal correlation and at last, the definition of the carbon intensity threshold. Furthermore, the selection of different system boundaries between CtG and WtG in the LCA did not show significant impacts on the LCOH. The average LCOH for additionality, considering all taxonomies, was 2687 JPY/kgH₂. The introduction of the additionality criteria resulted in substantially higher LCOH values due to the greater investment required to balance the lack of unconditional grid electricity. In contrast, the penetration of different levels of grid-supported electrolysis combined with the different carbon intensity levels offered a wide range of LCOH ranging from 2021 to 3399 JPY/kgH₂. Then, the impact of temporal matching requirements showed a correlation with the carbon intensity. On average, when comparing yearly to hourly correlation for all taxonomies, the LCOH became 15% more expensive. However, this value was accentuated for higher carbon intensity thresholds; 17% for the Chinese taxonomy versus 13.6% for the Japanese one. In the end, the more restrictive policies became, the higher but more stable and equal LCOH was achieved. The only exception is found when both hourly time matching and low carbon threshold are in place, which leads to exponential increase on price and even the unfeasibility of the most restrictive case.

Fig. 5, displays the results of the yearly average CIOH as a means to show the effect of the application of the different taxonomies.

Fig. 5. The effect of different carbon taxonomy on the CIOH. Legend: UK (United Kingdom), US (United States), CtG (Cradle-to-Gate), WtG (Well-to-Gate), H (hourly), M (monthly), Y (yearly).

Fig. 6. The effect of different carbon taxonomy on the Eco-Efficiency. Legend: UK (United Kingdom), US (United States), CtG (Cradle-to-Gate), WtG (Well-to-Gate), H (hourly), M (monthly), Y (yearly).

Additionality was also the most impactful criteria for all COIH results, achieving similar values between 1.17 and 1.44 kgCO₂-eq/kgH₂. Remarkably, yearly time correlation matched the carbon threshold of the taxonomy, then monthly and hourly time correlation showed an average increasingly lower value due to capping of the maximum emissions at higher time resolution. Significantly, the higher the carbon threshold, the higher the impact of time matching. Besides the UK taxonomy, hourly time matching produced COIH average values 51% lower than the targetted carbon threshold. In the case of the UK taxonomy, with a carbon threshold of 2 kgCO₂-eq/kgH₂, the variability of results in terms of emissions was reduced, showing that a lower carbon threshold reduced the dispatching options of the system, which may result in technical unfeasibility, or extensive costs.

The analysis of the yearly average EE results is included in Fig. 6. Furthermore, the hourly evolution of the EE for the baseline case was also studied in Fig. 7.

The results on EE showed a consistent higher EE value for WtG versus CtG system approach, particularly in the scenarios considering additionality of RES. Furthermore, at lower carbon threshold, yearly time matching became more eco-efficient. For instance, a carbon threshold of 2 kgCO₂-eq/kgH₂ at yearly time matching proved to be more eco-efficient than a higher carbon threshold of 3.4 kgCO₂-eq/kgH₂ at hourly time correlation. This result is also confirmed in the previous analysis of LCOH and COIH, opening the debate to whether time matching is really an effective mechanism to control carbon emissions. Specially, if its implementation at control level of the PtG plant is to be considered.

The highest EE values were found light-coloured in a vertical pattern corresponding to the WP supply and the minimum CIOH. A stable EE value following PV production predominated over the central hours of the day. The higher carbon intensity of PV-sourced electricity compared

Fig. 7. Hourly Eco-Efficiency (EE) applied to renewable hydrogen production, overview of a full year.

to wind-sourced power was weighted higher than the more competitive prices. This distribution shows that despite the PV’s lower electricity price compared to the WPPA, the last one’s lower carbon intensity has a higher impact on the EE of hydrogen. The lowest EE values are found during the night hours of the winter months, correlating with low RES availability periods. However, the analysis of the data proved that low EE values were not only associated with the grid’s electricity but also with low load factor operation, implying that operation can play a role on the analysed KPIs.

- Design and operation considerations:

The unfeasibility of the most demanding scenario considered, and the findings on the analysis of the EE at hourly level, were further addressed by looking into the design and operation of the PtG. Therefore, the wide range of LCOH results were associated with the different PtG designs achieved. Table 5 shows the resulting design strategy. The sizing of the PVPPA and WPPA has been neglected from the Table, both PPA options were maximised for all scenarios included in the study – 10MW for wind and 10 MWfor PV.

The operational restrictions when moving from a yearly grid-

supported scheme to an hourly correlation showed an increase in electrolyser and hydrogen storage size. The presence of BESS was not consistent throughout the different scenarios, mostly being included in hourly time matching or when additionality was implemented, and prioritised in CtG scenarios. The reason for this decision, was not economic but operational. When the manufacturing impact of the electrolyser is considered (CtG) there was not enough carbon emissions share left for the usage of the battery whose manufacturing impact is included in the use stage of the electricity discharged. Then, unlike in grid-connected setups, the capacity of the electrolyser was increased to maximise low-carbon hydrogen production during high RES availability periods. Similarly, to cope with the seasonal effects of RES, a higher hydrogen buffer was required in hourly matching scenarios.

In Fig. 8, the electrolyser’s overall load factor reached 76.7%, covered with up to 89% of RES. This was achieved through a consistent operation pattern during the central hours of the day due to the PV, but with a predominant role of WP at a 61% share per year. However, 48% of the power contracted via the WPPA was exported to the grid, compared to 8% for the PVPPA, which is not included in Fig. 8, indicating that the PPA was oversized. The grid’s power supply, despite making up only 11 %, accounted for the highest carbon intensity of the hydrogen’s production, peaking at 25.7 kgCO₂-eq per kg of H₂ – of the yearly average. Opposingly, WP supply achieved the lowest CIOH with 0.749 kgCO₂-eq/kgH₂.

Enabling additionality in Fig. 9 resulted in increased electrolyser capacity to accommodate a more flexible dispatch strategy - being able to produce more hydrogen in fewer hours following RES availability. However, this flexible operation accentuated an effect perceived in the valleys or vertical blanks of the image, which is that producing hydrogen at a low load factor even through RES, can correlate with high carbon intensity due to the accounting for the manufacturing impact of the electrolyser.

To better understand the correlation between low-load operation and high carbon intensity, Fig. 10 compares the manufacturing and use stage impacts at two different time resolutions. On a yearly basis, manufacturing impact only accounts for 4% of the overall carbon emissions associated with hydrogen production – which justifies the common assumption about it being negligible when compared to use stage impact over the lifetime of the electrolyser. However, when the same data is analysed at an hourly level, the contribution of the

Table 5

Power-to-gas designs for Japanese taxonomy. Legend: Time Correlation (TC), Electrolyser (ELY), Hydrogen Storage (HS), Battery Energy Storage System (BESS), Well-to-Gate (WtG), Cradle-to-Gate (CtG).

	Hourly TC			Monthly TC			Yearly TC		
	ELY (MW)	HS (tons)	BESS (MWh)	ELY (MW)	HS (tons)	BESS (MWh)	ELY (MW)	HS (tons)	BESS (MWh)
CtG: Additionality	4.22	22.1	0.96	4.22	22.3	0.18	4.23	22.1	0.17
CtG: Grid-connected	3.79	19.2	0.36	3.28	13.9	0	3.02	3.682	0
WtG: Additionality	4.12	22.1	1.85	4.14	22.1	1.57	4.24	24.1	0.02
WtG: Grid-connected	3.72	20.4	0.34	3.22	13.6	0	2.88	2.50	0

Fig. 8. Energy mix’s influence on the carbon intensity – Study of the Japanese taxonomy under grid-connected yearly matching correlation. Legend: Power Purchase Agreement (PPA), PV (Photovoltaic), Carbon Intensity of Hydrogen (CtGH).

Fig. 9. Energy mix's influence on the carbon intensity – Study of the Japanese taxonomy under additionality and hourly matching correlation. Legend: Power Purchase Agreement (PPA), PV (Photovoltaic), Battery Energy Storage System (BESS), Carbon Intensity of Hydrogen (CIOH).

Fig. 10. Manufacturing impact vs Use stage impact: A matter of time resolution.

manufacturing impact on the total share changes, reaching up to 70% of the total CIOH at certain time steps. This effect was found responsible for the unfeasibility of the CtG UK scenario. Increasing the capacity of the electrolyser due to a more restrictive taxonomy raises the baseline of the manufacturing impact, which reduces the range of operation of the electrolyser due to the impact on the CIOH. In the unfeasible case, the manufacturing impact of the required capacity of electrolyser to fulfil the demand is high enough to surpass the 2 kgCO₂-eq per kg of H₂ when low operation is required. Therefore, as observed in Fig. 10, the manufacturing impact, when accounted for at an hourly level, can highly impact the flexible operation and sizing of an electrolyser, which would be reason enough not to overlook it.

5. Conclusions

This study demonstrates the potential of the presented optimisation model to analyse and compare the implications of different policies, defined as carbon taxonomies, on the design and operation of PtG plants for renewable hydrogen production. The LCOH, CIOH, and EE metrics were selected to investigate the technical, economic, and environmental impacts of the criteria proposed in the most relevant carbon taxonomies: carbon intensity threshold, temporal matching requirements, the application of additionality and different system boundaries for the LCA, in particular CtG and WtG.

The findings confirmed the importance of additionality, extensive cost-competitive electricity supply, and the availability of a diversified low-carbon PPA portfolio. The evaluation of a case study in Japan also showed an LCOH of 2153 JPY/kgH₂, nearly seven times higher than the 2030 national target. The current Japanese FiT scheme for PPAs resulted on high LCOH values and a maximisation of the PPA capacity. Achieving lower volumetric tariffs for electrolytic hydrogen production would be an essential step for reducing the LCOH. Furthermore, increasing the surcharge price, could lead to disincentive the oversizing of PPAs portfolios and invest on BESS instead. The current Japanese FiT scheme

for PPAs resulted in high LCOH values and extensive PPA capacity. Securing lower volumetric tariffs for electrolytic hydrogen production is essential to lower LCOH. Additionally, increasing the surcharge price could discourage the oversizing of PPA portfolios by encouraging self-consumption through investment in BESS. In fact, while additionality is key to ensuring that electrolysis is linked to new RES deployment, it can also risk of oversizing both PtG plants and the PPA portfolio, which could led to wider negative systemic impacts. Regarding the temporal requirements, tightening the temporal resolution of the carbon accountability from yearly to monthly and hourly, proved to have an impact on the CIOH that surpassed the defined threshold. In this regard, grid-connected monthly temporal correlation could offer a good trade-off between cost and emissions.

This study also proved the importance, often disregarded in the literature, of manufacturing impact on hydrogen's hourly carbon intensity. Integrating LCA in the design of PtG plants is key for measuring the CIOH. However, if to be considered, the accountability for the manufacturing impacts needs to be included as part of the design and operation strategy - particularly in flexible operation. The consideration of hourly lifetime of the assets, and the application of hourly temporal correlations, led to interesting techno-environmental findings. The embodied carbon emissions were a limiting factor in the electrolyser operation at low load factor. Nevertheless, the use stage impact is the main driver for the CIOH. Hence, economies of scale and advantageous PPA schemes are key in reducing not only the LCOH, but also the CIOH. The implementation of BESS was increasingly important at higher resolution temporal matching requirements under additionality, but the manufacturing stage of the battery, considered in the use stage of the hydrogen production hindered its implementation in CtG-related scenarios. The consideration of CtG system boundaries, despite promoting a better accountability for carbon emissions, could hinder early hydrogen infrastructure deployment due to the wider implications in the operation and design. Hence, WtG system boundaries, benefitting from easier implementation are suggested.

The implementation of an EE metric for the evaluation of renewable hydrogen production proved to be a successful tool and showed to be more relevant at hourly level. Furthermore, the calculated EE metric can be used as a KPI for future multi-criteria optimisation of systems to explore the balance between environmental friendliness and cost-competitiveness.

Future research is still needed to evaluate the prospective environmental impacts of the different carbon taxonomies on future renewable hydrogen deployment scenarios. Moreover, understanding the systematic implications of renewable hydrogen production and the effects of carbon taxonomy could lead to finding a widely accepted definition of what is and how renewable hydrogen should be produced to facilitate fair global trade and ensure systemic decarbonisation.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

A. Martinez Alonso: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **D. Huber:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Conceptualization. **K. Komai:** Supervision. **M. Takeda:** Supervision. **T. Coosemans:** Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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